

Synthesis and evaluation of pharmacological activity of some new aminopyrimidine and thiopyrimidine derivatives

M. R. Patel, J. D. Akbari, D. H. Purohit and H. S. Joshi*

Department of Chemistry, Saurashtra University, Rajkot-360 005, Gujarat, India

E-mail : drhsjoshi@yahoo.com

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Abstract : Various 3-(2-amino-6-arylpyrimidin-4-yl)-6-chlorocinnolin-4(3H)-one (2a-j) and 6-chloro-3-(6-aryl-2-mercapto-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-4-yl)cinnolin-4(3H)-one (3a-j) were synthesized by the reaction of 6-chloro-3-[(2E)-3-arylprop-2-enoyl]-cinnolin-4(3H)-ones (1a-j) with guanidine hydrochloride and thiourea respectively. All newly synthesized compounds were tested against different microbes for their antimicrobial activity and *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* for their antitubercular activity.

Keywords : Aminopyrimidines, thiopyrimidines, microbial activities.

In the recent years much interest has been focused on the study of the cinnolin-4-one ring system because of its potential pharmacological activities¹⁻³. Aminopyrimidines and thiopyrimidines are also broadly found in bioorganic and medicinal chemistry with applications in drug discovery and developments. They are reported to possess broad spectrum of biological activities such as antibacterial⁴, fungicidal⁵, insecticidal⁶, antihypertensive⁷, tranquilizing⁸, analgesic⁹, antidiabetic¹⁰ etc. In light of above biological activities, it is worthwhile to synthesize aminopyrimidines and thiopyrimidines derivatives¹¹, which may have some good biological activities.

For the present investigation 6-chloro-3-[(2E)-3-arylprop-2-enoyl]cinnolin-4(3H)-ones (1a-j) were obtained from 3-acetyl-6-chlorocinnolin-4(3H)-one by the reaction with different aromatic aldehydes. Chalcones (1a-j) on the treatment with guanidine hydrochloride and thiourea in the presence of alcoholic potassium hydroxide in dioxane gave 3-(2-amino-6-arylpyrimidin-4-yl)-6-chlorocinnolin-4(3H)-ones (2a-j) and 6-chloro-3-(6-aryl-2-mercapto-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-4-yl)cinnolin-4(3H)-ones (3a-j) respectively. The structures of the synthesized compounds were assigned on the basis of elemental analysis, IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectral data (Table 1). The compounds have been screened for their *in vitro* antitubercular and antimicrobial activity (Table 2).

Results and discussion

Antitubercular activity :

The antitubercular evaluation of the compounds was

carried out at Tuberculosis Antimicrobial Acquisition Co-ordination Facility (TAACF), USA. Primary screening of the compounds for antitubercular activity have been conducted at 6.25 µg/ml towards *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H₃₇Rv in BACTEC 12B medium using the BACTEC 460 radiometric system. The compounds demonstrating at least >90% inhibitions in the primary screen have been compared with standard drug Rifampicin at 0.25 µg/ml concentrations and it showed 98% inhibition. The data % inhibitions are recorded in Table 2.

Antimicrobial activity :

The antimicrobial activity was assayed by using the cup-plate agar diffusion method¹² by measuring the zone of inhibition in mm. All the compounds were screened *in vitro* for their antimicrobial activity against varieties of bacterial strains such as *Bacillus megaterium*, *Staphylococcus subtilis*, *Escherichia coli*, *Proteus vulgaris* and fungi *Aspergillus niger* at 40 µg/ml concentration. Standard drugs like Amoxicillin, Norfloxacin, Benzyl penicillin, Ampicillin and Griseofulvin were used for the comparison purpose (Table 2).

Experimental

Thin layer chromatography was used to access the reactions and purity of the compounds synthesized. The melting points were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on Shimadzu FT-IR-8400 instrument in KBr disc and only principle sharply defined peaks are recorded (ν_{\max} in cm⁻¹). ¹H NMR spectra on a Bruke AC-300 MHz FT NMR

Table 1. Characterization data of compounds 1a-j, 2a-j and 3a-j

Compd.	R	Mol. formula	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	N (%) Calcd. (Found)	¹ H NMR (in δ, ppm)	
						X	Ar-H
1a	C ₆ H ₅ -	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ O ₂	210	74	9.02 (9.02)	-	6.99-8.04 (11H, m)
1b	3-Br-C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ BrClN ₂ O ₂	198	71	7.19 (7.15)	-	6.98-8.06 (10H, m)
1c	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂	220	72	8.12 (8.11)	-	6.95-8.03 (10H, m)
1d	3-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂	174	65	8.12 (8.06)	-	6.91-8.00 (10H, m)
1e	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂	170	59	8.12 (8.08)	-	6.92-7.98 (10H, m)
1f	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ O ₄	178	64	7.56 (7.54)	3.88 (6H, s)	6.92-8.02 (9H, m)
1g	4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ ClN ₂ O ₃	190	68	8.22 (8.20)	3.86 (3H, s)	6.99-8.04 (10H, m)
1h	4-SCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₃ -	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	204	54	7.85 (7.83)	2.82 (6H, s)	6.80-7.92 (7H, m)
1i	3-C ₆ H ₅ -O-C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₂₃ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ O ₃	181	60	6.95 (6.94)	-	6.90-7.95 (15H, m)
1j	4-N(CH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ O ₂	194	50	11.88 (11.84)	2.56 (6H, s)	6.93-8.05 (10H, m)
2a	C ₆ H ₅ -	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ ClN ₅ O	245	56	20.02 (20.01)	-	5.43-8.74 (12H, m)
2b	3-Br-C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ BrN ₅ O ₂	230	54	16.34 (16.32)	-	5.40-8.72 (11H, m)
2c	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₅ O	282	49	18.23 (18.22)	-	5.42-8.72 (11H, m)
2d	3-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₅ O	180	48	18.23 (18.21)	-	5.38-8.71 (11H, m)
2e	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₅ O	134	47	18.23 (18.23)	-	5.43-8.74 (11H, m)
2f	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃ -	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ ClN ₅ O ₂	308	45	20.61 (20.58)	3.80 (6H, s)	5.43-8.74 (4H, m)
2g	4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ ClN ₅ O ₂	304	46	18.44 (18.42)	3.78 (3H, s)	5.43-8.74 (11H, m)
2h	4-SCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₃ -	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ ClN ₅ OS	260	48	17.69 (17.66)	2.48 (6H, s)	5.43-8.74 (8H, m)
2i	3-C ₆ H ₅ -O-C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ ClN ₅ O ₂	175	52	15.85 (15.81)	-	5.36-8.65 (16H, m)
2j	4-N(CH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ ClN ₆ O	160	53	21.39 (21.38)	2.43 (3H, s)	5.36-8.42 (14H, m)
3a	C ₆ H ₅ -	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ ClN ₄ OS	149	54	15.19 (15.17)	-	6.61-8.41 (13H, m)
3b	3-Br-C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ BrN ₄ OS	108	54	12.51 (12.50)	-	6.58-8.42 (12H, m)
3c	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ N ₄ OS	156	56	13.89 (13.88)	-	6.55-8.46 (13H, m)
3d	3-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ N ₄ OS	182	55	13.89 (13.87)	-	6.65-8.38 (13H, m)
3e	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ N ₄ OS	188	53	13.89 (13.88)	-	6.70-8.55 (13H, m)
3f	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ ClN ₄ O ₃ S	290	58	13.06 (13.04)	3.80 (6H, s)	6.62-8.51 (11H, m)
3g	4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ ClN ₄ O ₂ S	178	49	14.05 (14.03)	3.87 (3H, s)	6.73-8.54 (12H, m)
3h	4-SCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₃ -	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ ClN ₄ OS ₂	145	47	13.50 (13.47)	2.68 (6H, s)	6.72-8.52 (9H, m)
3i	3-C ₆ H ₅ -O-C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ ClN ₄ O ₂ S	188	50	12.16 (12.15)	-	6.65-8.52 (17H, m)
3j	4-N(CH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₂₀ H ₁₃ ClN ₅ OS	164	54	17.00 (12.98)	2.56 (3H, s)	6.58-8.55 (10H, m)

spectrophotometer using TMS as internal reference (chemical shift in δ ppm). Mass spectra were recorded at Jeol D-300 spectrometer. All the synthesized compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

Preparation of 6-chloro-3-[(2E)-3-aryl-prop-2-enoyl]cinnolin-4(3H)-one (1a-j) :

A mixture of 3-acetyl-6-chlorocinnolin-4(3H)-one (0.01 mol, 2.23 g) and anisaldehyde (0.01 mol, 3.6 g) in 30 ml of dioxane was stirred at room temperature for 24 h in the presence of 5 ml of 40% KOH. The mixture was poured on crushed ice, the separated solid was isolated and crystallized from alcohol to gave **1g**, yield 68% (2.31 g), m.p. 190 °C (Found : C, 63.42; H, 3.84; N, 8.20.

C₁₈H₁₃ClN₂O₃ required : C, 63.44; H, 3.84; N, 8.22%); IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) spectra of the compounds showed bands at 2927 (CH-CH str.), 1661 (C=O, carbonyl), 1238 (C-O-C str.), 740 (C-Cl str.); ¹H NMR (300 MHz CDCl₃ + DMSO-*d*₆) δ ppm : 8.04 (2H, dd, Ar-H_b *p*-sub), 7.26-7.79 (6H, m, Ar-H), 6.99 (2H, dd, Ar-H_a *p*-sub), 3.86 (3H, s, Ar-OCH₃). Mass spectra of compound exhibited molecular ion peak at *m/z* 341 (M⁺), other important fragments were observed at 154 (M⁺).

Similarly, compounds **1a-j** were prepared by the condensation of 3-acetyl-6-chlorocinnolin-4(3H)-one with other aromatic aldehydes and their characterization data are recorded in Table 1.

Note

Preparation of 3-[2-amino-6-aryl-pyrimidin-4-yl]-6-chlorocinnolin-4(3H)-one (**2a-j**) :

To a solution of 6-chloro-3-[(*E*)-3-aryl-prop-2-enoyl]cinnolin-4(3H)-one (0.01 mol, 3.4 g) guanidine hy-

$C_{19}H_{14}ClN_5O_2$ required : C, 60.09; H, 3.72; N, 18.44%; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) spectra of the compounds showed bands at 3267-3355 (N-H str.), 2920 (CH-CH str.), 1679 (C=O, carbonyl), 734 (C-Cl str.), 1168 (C-O-C str.); 1H NMR

drochloride (0.01mol, 1.10 g) was added and the content was refluxed in the presence of 2 ml alcoholic KOH for 8 h. The excess solvent was distilled off and the residue was neutralized with 20% HCl, the product was isolated and crystallized from ethanol to give **2g**, yield 46% (1.75 g), m.p. 304 °C (Found : C, 60.05; H, 3.70; N, 18.42.

(300 MHz $CDCl_3 + DMSO-d_6$) δ ppm : 8.74 (2H, s, $Ar-NH_2$), 7.96 (2H, d, $Ar-H_b$ *p*-sub), 7.36-7.90 (3H, m, $Ar-H$), 7.30 (2H, s, $Ar-H_a$ *p*-sub), 7.25 (1H, m, cinnolin- H_d), 5.34 (1H, s, $Ar-CH_c$), 3.78 (3H, s, $Ar-CH_3$). Mass spectra of compound exhibited molecular ion peak at m/z 380 (M^+).

Table 2. Antitubercular and antimicrobial screening results of compounds 1a-j, 2a-j and 3a-j

Compd.	% Inhibition Antitubercular activity	Zones of inhibition in mm				
		Antibacterial activity				Antifungal activity
		<i>B. mega</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. vulgaris</i>	
1a	20	11	14	15	15	12
1b	12	12	15	12	11	15
1c	19	15	11	11	13	17
1d	22	16	11	15	11	13
1e	32	12	13	12	14	14
1f	14	13	12	15	14	15
1g	21	15	11	12	15	11
1h	25	12	15	11	18	15
1i	26	14	15	15	15	12
1j	65	11	14	15	14	14
2a	21	19	13	24	12	15
2b	17	19	18	15	11	11
2c	36	14	12	12	14	13
2d	51	12	15	17	21	18
2e	24	20	12	22	24	12
2f	2	18	15	12	16	21
2g	9	15	13	20	15	17
2h	32	15	14	17	12	12
2i	4	17	11	13	10	14
2j	29	26	12	12	13	18
3a	63	14	13	18	18	11
3b	25	15	12	12	14	15
3c	45	12	10	13	14	16
3d	21	14	15	18	16	12
3e	11	13	19	19	15	14
3f	20	10	13	17	14	16
3g	14	18	14	13	17	18
3h	32	15	16	15	14	12
3i	20	17	17	18	18	14
3j	19	16	19	22	23	12
Ampicillin	-	20	24	21	22	00
Norfloxacin	-	18	17	25	24	00
Benzylpenicillin	-	20	18	15	18	00
Amoxicillin	-	21	24	25	25	00
Griseofulvin	-	00	00	00	00	22

Similarly, compounds 2a-j were prepared by the condensation of 6-chloro-3-[(2E)-3-aryl-prop-2-enoyl]cinnolin-4(3H)-one 1a-j with guanidine hydrochloride and their characterization data are recorded in Table 1.

Preparation of 6-chloro-3-[6-aryl-2-mercapto-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-4-yl]cinnolin-4(3H)-one (3a-j) :

A mixture of 6-chloro-3-[(2E)-3-(4-methoxyphenyl)prop-2-enoyl]cinnolin-4(3H)-one 1g (0.01 mol, 3.4 g) and thiourea (0.01 mol, 0.78 g) in dry dioxane in the presence of alcoholic potassium hydroxide was refluxed for 10 h on water bath. The excess solvent was distilled off and the residue was neutralized with diluted HCl, the

product was isolated and crystallized from ethanol to give **3g**, yield 51% (2.03 g), m.p. 200 °C (Found : C, 61.10; H, 3.40; N, 11.84. C₁₉H₁₅ClN₄O₂S required : C, 61.11; H, 3.42; N, 11.88%); IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) spectra of the compounds showed bands at 2935 (CH-CH str.), 1679 (C=O str., carbonyl), 765 (C-Cl str.), 1161 (C-O-C str.); ¹H NMR ((300 MHz CDCl₃ + DMSO-*d*₆) δ ppm : 8.41 (1H, s, Ar-NH), 7.80 (2H, d, Ar-H_b *p*-sub), 7.97 (1H, d, Ar-H_d), 7.78 (2H, s, Ar-H_a *p*-sub), 7.69 (1H, m, cinnolin-H_e), 7.36–7.45 (3H, m, Ar-H), 6.61 (1H, s, Ar-CH_c), 3.78 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃), 1.53 (1H, s, -SH). Mass spectra of compound exhibited molecular ion peak at *m/z* 390 (M⁺), other important fragments were observed at 154 (M⁺).

Similarly, compounds **3a-j** were prepared by the condensation of 6-chloro-3-[(*2E*)-3-aryl-prop-2-enoyl]cinnolin-4(3*H*)-one **1a-j** with thiourea and their characterization data are recorded in Table 1.

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